

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Sorption of recalcitrant phosphonates in reverse osmosis concentrates and wastewater effluents – influence of metal ions

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Analytical methods

All standard wastewater parameters presented in Table 1 in the main paper were analyzed following their respective DIN standards.

Dissolved ortho-phosphate concentrations of all samples were determined spectrophotometrically after membrane filtration (0.45 μm) with the ammonium molybdate method according to the German standard DIN-EN-ISO 6878, 2004 and are typically presented as elemental $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$. Spectrophotometer Shimadzu UV-1800 in absorbance mode (880 nm) was used to record UV-vis extinction spectra and correlate them with the corresponding phosphate concentrations. Other anions (SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , F^- , Br^- , etc.) and ammonium (NH_4^+) were determined according to DIN-EN-ISO 10304-1/14911 with ion chromatographer Dionex ICS-1100 from Thermo Fischer Scientific.

Total carbon (TC) and total organic carbon (TOC) were measured with a Vario Cube analyzer from Elementar based on DIN-EN 1484. Total inorganic carbon ($\text{TIC} \approx \text{HCO}_3^-$) was calculated as the difference between TC and TOC.

COD was determined with cell tests using a DR-3900 from Hach-Lange.

All metals were analyzed after microwave sample digestion in $\text{HNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) device NexION 350X from Perkin–Elmer, following DIN-EN-ISO 17294-1. The samples had to be digested in advance with nitric acid (HNO_3) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) in a microwave oven.

Total suspended solids (TSS) and dry residue (at 105 $^\circ\text{C}$) were defined according to DIN 38409.

Electrical conductivity was measured with a WTW-TetraCon-925 probe and WTW-Multi-3430 device. Temperature and pH were measured with a Greisinger-3551 pH and temperature meter and a Greisinger-GE-117 pH electrode.

Laboratory-scale experiments with synthetic phosphonate solutions

Experimental procedure – effect of pH and adsorbent dose on phosphonate removal

Curves depicting the adsorption capacity as a function of pH were represented by the logistic function model (LFM, Equation S1). The parameters a , b , and d were determined using the least squares method.

$$q(\text{pH}) = \frac{d}{(1+ae^{-b \times \text{pH}})} \quad (\text{S1})$$

The coefficient of determination r^2 was calculated with Equation S2. Here, q_i is the experimentally measured data, \bar{q}_i is the mean value of the data and q_m the data determined with the model function.

$$r^2 = \frac{\sum (q_m - \bar{q}_i)^2}{\sum (q_m - \bar{q}_i)^2 + \sum (q_m - q_i)^2} \quad (\text{S2})$$

Adsorption kinetics were modeled either with the pseudo-first-order model (Equation S3) or with the pseudo-second-order model (Equation S4) after converting the equations into their linear forms in order to determine the constants q_e , k_1 , and k_2 , as follows:

$$q(t) = q_e(1-e^{-k_1 t}) \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$q(t) = \frac{q_e^2 k_2 t}{1+q_e k_2 t} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Adsorption isotherms were modeled using either the Freundlich (Equation S5) or the Langmuir equation (Equation S6) in their linear forms to determine the constants K_F , K_L , q_{max} , and n :

$$q(c) = K_F c^{1/n} \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$q(c) = q_{max} \frac{K_L c}{1+K_L c} \quad (\text{S6})$$

Pilot-scale adsorbent reusability experiment for municipal effluent polishing

Figure S2 | The pilot-scale setup consisted of a 200 L adsorption reactor in which municipal effluent wastewater was treated with the magnetic particles in 55 consecutive cycles. Phosphorus adsorption was performed in a batch mode, followed by separation of the particles with a drum magnetic separator (bottom right), intermediate storage of the effluent in a buffer tank and second-stage high-gradient magnetic separation (HGMS). Phosphorus desorption and regeneration of the particles were carried out in a smaller 30 L desorption reactor (bottom left).

Afterwards the regenerated particles were magnetically separated and reintroduced into the adsorption reactor for the next cycle.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH on phosphonate removal at a fixed adsorbent dosage

Table S1 | Model constants and coefficients of determination for the logistic function model describing the loading of NTMP (initial concentration: 1 mg/L NTMP-P) onto 0.03 g/L ZnFeZr adsorbent as a function of pH at room temperature and 30 min contact time ($d = 33.333 \text{ mg P/g} (= 1 \text{ mg/L NTMP-P}/0.03 \text{ g/L})$ as maximum loading)

	H ₃ PO ₄	HEDP	NTMP	EDTMP
a [-]	6.37×10^{-5}	5.35×10^{-4}	1.80×10^{-5}	7.79×10^{-6}
b [-]	-1.4107	-0.9466	-1.7841	-1.8148
r ²	0.984	0.986	0.990	0.986

Effect of pH on NTMP removal at various adsorbent dosages; NTMP adsorption kinetics and isotherms

In the case of 0.1 g/L adsorbent, a clear difference in the adsorption rate between pH 6 and 7 could be observed (Figure S3(a)). At pH 6, almost-complete adsorption of NTMP was achieved within a relatively short period of time, whereas at pH 7 adsorption equilibrium could not be reached even after 8 hours. The dosage of 0.4 g/L adsorbent led to a fast and almost complete adsorption at both pH values. Both kinetics at pH 6 were most accurately modeled with the pseudo-second-order type 3 (PSOT3), the course at pH 7 and 0.4 g/L using PSOT4, and the course at pH 7 and 0.1 g/L using the pseudo-first-order kinetics (Table S2). For the latter sample, the coefficients of determination of all PSOs were between 0.45 and 0.83 only.

NTMP adsorption isotherms at pH 6 and three different temperatures, modeled with the Freundlich and Langmuir functions, are included in Figure S3(b). The calculated model constants and coefficients are listed in Table S3.

Figure S3 | **a) Adsorption kinetics:** Removal of 1 mg/L NTMP-P with ZnFeZr@MP as a function of time with adsorbent concentrations 0.1 g/L and 0.4 g/L at pH 6 and pH 7 at room temperature (22 °C), fitted with pseudo-first-order kinetic model (PFO) or pseudo-second-order (PSO, type 3 or 4);
b) Adsorption isotherms of 1 mg/L NTMP-P onto ZnFeZr@MP (0.009–0.100 g/L adsorbent) at different temperatures, pH 6 and 30 min contact time, fitted with Freundlich (solid lines) and Langmuir (dashed lines) models.

Figure S3(b) shows the increase in loading with increase in temperature. For example, at pH 6 and 30 min contact time, almost complete elimination of 1 mg/L NTMP-P was achieved at 35 °C with about 60 mg/L adsorbent, whereas at room temperature about 100 mg/L were required. This indicates that the adsorption of phosphonates on ZnFeZr oxyhydroxides might be endothermic. Furthermore, all adsorption isotherms were most accurately modeled using the Freundlich equation (Table S3), suggesting a multilayer adsorption process.

Table S2 | Equilibrium loads, adsorption rate constants and coefficients of determination of adsorption kinetics at room temperature and different pH values and different ZnFeZr adsorbent concentrations (initial concentration: 1 mg/L NTMP-P)

Adsorbent	pH	Model	q_e [mg _{ads} /L]	k_1 [1/h] or k_2 [(L/(mg _{ads} ·h))]	r^2
0.1 g/L	6	PSOT3	1.06	10.00	0.994
0.4 g/L	6	PSOT3	1.04	43.82	0.977
0.1 g/L	7	PFO	0.87	0.66	0.919
0.4 g/L	7	PSOT4	0.97	89.32	0.988

Table S3 | Model constants and coefficients of determination for adsorption isotherms of ZnFeZr adsorbent at different temperatures and pH 6 (initial concentration: 1 mg/L NTMP-P)

Temperature	Freundlich			Langmuir		
	n	K_F	r^2	q_{max}	K_L	r^2
	–	(mg/g)/(mg/L) ⁿ	–	mg/g	L/mg	–
6 °C	2.098	8.098	0.454	10.280	2.934	0.439
22 °C	5.821	19.091	0.940	17.552	75.088	0.671
35 °C	6.861	24.182	0.940	22.247	112.97	0.931

Reference

Rott, E., Nouri, M., Meyer, C., Minke, R., Schneider, M., Mandel, K. & Drenkova-Tuhtan, A. 2018 Removal of phosphonates from synthetic and industrial wastewater with reusable magnetic adsorbent particles. *Water Research*, **145**, 608–617.